

Exclusive Pulmonary Involvement in Erdheim-Chester Disease: A Rare Presentation

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ABSTRACT

Erdheim-Chester disease (ECD) is a rare condition classified as a non-Langerhans cell histiocytosis.

We present a case of 40-year-old man with dyspnea and chronic cough. Thoracic CT scan showed bilateral pulmonary consolidations.

Histological study of the CT guided biopsy revealed a proliferation of large cells with histiocytic features. On immunohistochemistry, the CD68 marker showed positive staining and confirmed the histiocytic nature of these large cells, which also expressed CD45, CD79, and CD99. In contrast, the staining of the histiocytic cells was negative for CD1a.

CASE REPORT

A 40-year-old man with no past medical history presented to pulmonology department for evaluation of a dyspnea and chronic cough. The clinical examination was normal, but the clinical course was marked by a weight loss and deterioration in general condition.

The patient underwent a bronchoscopy which came back normal. However, a thoracic CT scan showed bilateral pulmonary consolidations.

Histological study of the CT guided biopsy revealed a proliferation of large cells with histiocytic features. They are arranged in sheets and surrounded by reactive inflammatory infiltrate composed of lymphocytes and neutrophils. (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Histological aspects of Erdheim-Chester disease in Hematoxylin and Eosin staining (H&E), showing a proliferation of histiocytic cells surrounded by a reactive inflammatory infiltrate. (A) H&x10; (B) H&E x 40.

On immunohistochemistry, the CD68 marker showed positive staining and confirmed the histiocytic nature of these large cells, which also expressed CD45, CD79, and CD99. The CD4, CD5, and CD20 markers highlighted a reactive B and T lymphoid population.

In contrast, the staining of the histiocytic cells was negative for CD1a, EMA, PS100, AE1/AE3, Pax5, CD30, MPO, TdT and langerin markers. (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Immunohistochemical findings: Positive staining of histiocytic cells with CD68 and negative staining for CD1a.

Based on the morphological aspects and immunohistochemical study, the diagnosis of Erdheim-Chester histiocytosis was established.

DISCUSSION

Erdheim-Chester disease (ECD) is a rare condition that was first described in 1930. It is classified as a non-Langerhans cell histiocytosis.^[1] 500 to 550 cases approximately have been documented in the literature worldwide, with an increase in recognition over recent years.^[2] It most commonly affects adults between the fourth and sixth decades of life, with a male-to-female ratio of 3:1.^[3]

The diagnosis of Erdheim-Chester is based on histopathological study with a suggestive clinical and radiological context. Its natural history is very variable and depends on the extent and distribution of clinical involvement. This histiocytosis can range from very limited, single-tissue involvement to multisystemic forms that can be life-threatening.

The Immunohistological features of the histiocytic cells in this disease help distinguish it from Langerhans cell histiocytosis. In Erdheim-Chester histiocytosis, immunostaining is positive for CD68 and negative CD1a. In contrast, both CD68 and CD1a markers are positive in Langerhans cell histiocytosis. Moreover, in most cases of Erdheim-Chester disease, S100 marker is negative.^[2]

The medical management of patients has marked a significant advancement due to the introduction of interferon-alpha. In the past, the mortality rate was around 60% and a mean survival of 19 months. Currently, with interferon-alpha treatment, 5-year survival rates have improved substantially, reaching 68%, and overall mortality has decreased to 26%.^[4]

CONCLUSION

The course of Erdheim-Chester histiocytosis is chronic and with no spontaneous regression. For this reason, it is crucial not to overlook this rare presentation and to ensure long-term follow-up of affected patients.

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